

The Future of Federated X-haul and Wireless Access in 6G Era

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Abstract—The sixth generation of mobile communication (6G) networks has gained significant interest, introducing new use case families. Their requirements for higher bit rate, lower latency, and a higher number of connections will push future mobile networks to a new era in which various novelties related to sensing, positioning, and imaging, as well as intelligent computing, among others, will play critical roles and via their convergence, the network will be able to will support their demands. The integration of techniques developed for wireless communications with those designed for IP/Optical X-haul will be an essential step in realizing the concept of the Federation of the (Cognitive) Digital Twins of the different network (sub)-segments (FDTN). The FDTN will interconnect the various Digital Twins (DT) of the different 6G sub-networks and domains, enabling the sharing of information between them, e.g., data, Machine Learning (ML) models, etc. In this context, this paper discusses the next logical steps, which include the required innovations in the optical and the wireless part of the network as well as the realization of an FDTN to optimize the design and network operation end-to-end, improve the overall network performance, and maximize the overall reliability shaping a seamlessly integrated ultra-energy-efficient Digital-Twin enhanced 6G network over all its segments and domains.

Keywords—6G, Digital Twin, X-haul, Optical Wireless Communications, Optical Fiber Communications.

I. INTRODUCTION

The "IMT-2030 Framework" has defined six new use case categories that enable a wide range of services for end-users [1], predicting an unprecedented growth in overall mobile communication traffic. According to various estimates, mobile data traffic is expected to surge from approximately 200 exabytes (EB) per month in 2023 to over 1000 EB by 2030. To meet these increasing traffic demands, innovations across various dimensions—network segments, layers, and technologies (both software and hardware related)—are necessary to define how 6G networks will be shaped [2]-[4].

The 6G networks will be able to utilize both millimeter-wave (mm-Wave) and terahertz (THz) connectivity alongside Optical Wireless Communication (OWC) technologies. By

deploying on-demand virtualized small cells (pico/femto) operating at high-end mm-Wave and THz frequencies, combined with OWC, these networks will leverage an intelligent optical-wireless Radio Access Network (OWRAN) architecture. Additionally, a dynamic and flexible Cloud Radio Access Network (C-RAN) environment will be employed to enable controlled centralization, ensuring the seamless integration of these advanced connectivity solutions.

The holistic representation and end-to-end monitoring and optimization of the 6G network can be achieved through a two-step procedure. The first step is the development of a Digital Twin (DT) for each network segment, e.g., i) all "Xs" of the X-haul, ii) all sub-segments of the core network, and iii) all sub-segments of the OWRAN. The second step is the implementation of the Federation of these (Cognitive) Digital Twins of the different network (sub)-segments (FDTN). This approach will enable information sharing between the different sub-segments and federations in various forms, e.g. data, locally trained Machine Learning (ML) models, etc. In this way, the design, operation and optimization of end-to-end 6G network will be realized.

The DT-based approach has already been proposed for specific application scenarios in [5]-[8]. In [5], the authors present a vision of an Internet of Federated Digital Twins (IoFDT) to holistically integrate heterogeneous and physically separated DTs representing different Society 5.0 services into a single framework, discussing various aspects and providing recommendations to realize this vision. The work of [6] analyzes a vision of how Artificial Intelligence (AI) tools will complement DTs and assist with overcoming their limitations. Finally, the works of [7], [8] are discussing DT's role and positive impact on optical communication systems and addressing various tasks, such as fault management, hardware configuration, etc.

In this work, we aim to go one step further by proposing to federate all different (sub)-segments of the 6G network by creating a federation of DTs developed for each sub-segment/sub-domain. The proposed approach pictorially described in Fig.1 comprises the fixed IP/optical X-haul and wireless OWRAN subnetworks. The OWRAN should control

the legacy Access Point (AP) equipment, the far-edge cloud, the Internet of Things (IoT) and non-terrestrial networks (NTN). The IP/Optical X-haul is connected to the optical front/mid/backhaul continuum and to the transport segment, and the Core Network is responsible for the interaction between different computing devices located mainly far from the end-user. Also, the computing can be located in the devices on some occasions. The DTs of those subnetworks give rise to the term “Digital Twins of Federated Networks.”

In the next sections, we present our perspective on the design and operation of future 6G networks and the innovative components that need to be developed to address the 6G-related challenges [1]. Specifically, we propose a new vision based on the convergence of Optical Fiber Communication (OFC) with OWC technologies (section 2) and the proposal of a new concept interconnecting different network domains and segments based on their respective DTs named FDTN (section 3).

II. OPTICAL FIBER COMMUNICATION AND OPTICAL WIRELESS COMMUNICATIONS INNOVATIONS

To meet the 6G network demands, a new generation of Coherent (COH) technologies must be introduced into access networks, following the example of their implementation in backbone networks over the past 15 years. These technologies leverage COH detection to provide superior connectivity solutions, enabling improved performance through increased system margins, adaptive high-order modulations, and real-time Digital Signal Processing (DSP) optimization. The design of these COH systems must take into account the low-cost and low-power requirements of access networks while enhancing the capabilities of legacy OFC and OWC systems, which now rely on older Intensity Modulation and Direct Detection (IM/DD) techniques.

The IP/Optical X-haul segment of 6G networks should efficiently aggregate the huge wireless access segment’s traffic, where massive deployments of Multiple Input Multiple Output (MIMO) micro/pico/femto-cells are expected. To support this traffic, it will be primarily based on advanced OFC technologies and components, e.g. transceivers, optical nodes etc., like the ones developed in the EU-funded projects PROTEUS-6G [9] and FLEX-SCALE [10]. Some wireless systems may also be utilized to handle traffic by implementing statistical multiplexing and traffic grooming. In 6G, the RAN may be augmented with OWC, giving rise to a seamlessly integrated OWRAN as depicted in the left part of Fig.2. OWC

encompasses systems that operate at visible and/or infrared wavelengths that can serve both indoor and outdoor use-case scenarios (from short range distribution to long point-to-point links). Several technologies can be included, such as Free Space Optics (FSO), Light-Fidelity (Li-Fi), Visible Light Communications (VLC) and Optical Camera Communications (OCC). FSO are systems that typically employ laser transmitters and are used for longer-range point-to-point terrestrial (e.g., 5G backhaul) and outdoor space communications, while Li-Fi and VLC typically employ Light-Emitting-Diodes (LEDs) and are utilized in shorter-range point-to-multi-point access (LiFi/VLC) and device-to-device (D2D) indoor communications (OCC). Occasionally, OFC and OWC systems can also be deployed in hybrid configurations, as in the case of Fiber-Wireless-Fiber (Fi-Wi-Fi) scenarios (which may also use THz technology for wireless connectivity, as a “virtual extension” of OFC systems).

The new COH access infrastructure will be built on foundational optical technologies that extend internet access everywhere, utilizing fixed OFC Fiber to the Home (FTTH) and Fiber to the Antenna (FTTA) infrastructures, as well as OWC Fiber to the Sky (FTTS) wireless connectivity as shown in Fig.2. This includes the deployment of LiFi and FSO systems with photonics-based optical beamforming capabilities, which offer exciting possibilities for network monitoring and sensing by extracting information from COH receivers.

Data gathered from these systems, alongside other optics-based techniques, will help assess the optical signal quality for each carrier transmitted over OFC and OWC systems and evaluate the quality of the associated optical channels, whether fixed or wireless. Additionally, these technologies will collect information about various parameters, such as loss and dispersion, and the infrastructure in which they are deployed, like buildings, roads, and bridges. This approach essentially transforms the communications infrastructure into a distributed wide-area network sensor. Also, by launching light pulses through optical fibers or over the air, valuable insights into the network’s “health” and the surrounding environment can be obtained.

Integrating these communication, monitoring, and sensing capabilities with AI and ML has the potential to simplify network management, making it more intelligent and automated. Several critical issues need to be addressed to fully exploit the potential of COH access networks in integrating

Fig. 1. The concept of Digital Twins of Federated Networks.

OFC, OWC, and sensing in FTTH, FTTA, and FTTS scenarios. These include developing new photonic devices and subsystems tailored for COH OFC and OWC, incorporating monitoring and sensing capabilities into the network for proactive maintenance and resource allocation, and implementing intelligent control systems that employ AI and ML to analyze network data and make dynamic adjustments. These advancements will revolutionize the access network landscape, creating new market opportunities and improving the overall quality of life for the entire society.

A. Optical Wireless Communications for 6G

The OWC systems have attracted significant interest across various applications and scenarios. Notably, there is a growing focus within the 3GPP on delivering high-rate (>1 Gb/s) connectivity to airborne entities and NTN. Enabling connectivity to flying objects facilitates seamless network integration, offering rapid data access and serving as an efficient relay for signal distribution in remote or emergency situations [11]. Current efforts primarily target the sub-6GHz spectrum, albeit the speed limitations. While FSO links present an optimal choice for high-speed connections, there is limited empirical validation of their feasibility.

The primary challenges associated with FSO channels arise from atmospheric attenuation and turbulence, which pose difficulties for COH FSO signal reception. Rapid fluctuations in received power, known as power fading events, result in swiftly changing signal conditions and Signal-to-Noise Ratio (SNR). This dynamic environment presents a significant hurdle for COH DSP, necessitating adaptive capacity and robustness against signal loss during intense fading events. COH signal combining using photodetector arrays is promising in mitigating fading events, but it increases complexity, a challenge to be addressed through specialized hardware component development.

OWC, commonly referred to as Li-Fi, can deliver high data rates to users in indoor settings where Radio Frequency (RF) may not be suitable or acceptable due to security concerns. Developing OWC systems capable of integrating sensing functionalities with communication presents another challenge. For instance, indoor navigation, obstacle detection, and distance ranging can benefit from integrated solutions that leverage OWC technology for enhanced functionality and performance. Developing OWC systems that can combine Integrated Sensing and Communications (OWC-ISAC) is also challenging. For example, indoor navigation, obstacle

detection, and distance ranging can rely on similar solutions. Alternatively, positioning, localization, and beam direction can be supported by dedicated light-based Light Detection and Ranging (LiDAR) systems with high resolution.

In addition, at the emitted beams of an OWC transmitter, the concept of Frequency Modulated Continuous Wave (FMCW) can be used for sensing. For this scenario, the same transceiver can be exploited where a Voltage-Controlled Oscillator (VCO) drives a Mach-Zehnder Interferometer (MZI)-based modulator to create a Carrier-Suppressed, Single-Side Band (CS-SSB) signal, the frequency of which is linearly modulated in time (saw-tooth type periodic modulation) in the range of 10 to 20 GHz. The OWC receiver detects the reflected signal from an object, and when mixed with the on-chip laser signal, it produces a beat frequency when the mixed signal is detected by a balanced photodiode. The value of the beat frequency is determined by the distance between the transmitter and the object, and DSP is used to retrieve this distance. In principle, the object's velocity can also be retrieved by measuring the beat frequency during the up- and down-ramp of the single sideband frequency.

It is our view that new optical wireless networks need to be accompanied by an intelligent sensing infrastructure capable of assisting the communication links in adapting to sudden network changes and variations in the wireless channel or operational environment in a highly flexible and dynamic way. In that direction, the capabilities of optical wireless sensing techniques should be augmented via the exploitation of state-of-the-art monitoring equipment (e.g., 4D-LiDARs) to continuously monitor the location of obstacles, user movements and the impact of local weather conditions. This approach can significantly improve the efficiency and performance of OWC communication links by taking advantage of the data available from the COH receivers and other external Commercial Off-The-Shelf (COTS) sensing equipment.

B. Optical Fiber Communication innovations for 6G

The optical X-haul must be enhanced with advanced optical networking technologies. These enhancements include: 1) the development of high-rate, flexible, and energy-efficient optical transceivers capable of operating at rates exceeding 800 Gb/s, 2) the increase of optical transmission capacity through the use of Ultra-Wide-Band (UWB) or Spatial Division Multiplexing (SDM) to achieve capacities greater than 1 Pb/s per link, 3) the deployment of more flexible

Fig. 2. Multi-technology network scenario targeting FTTH, FTTA, and FTTS deployment scenarios based on OWC technologies and a multi-access controller performing intelligent computation exploiting end-user data (left part of the figure). The networking scenario brings together multiple communication technologies (both optical and wireless) from the various network domains.

and faster all-optical switching technologies that increasingly rely on UWB/SDM, implemented using integrated programmable photonics devices, to achieve switching durations of less than 10 ms, and 4) the integration of intelligent control systems based on energy-efficient resource management to enable end-to-end orchestration of the entire X-haul.

To implement these innovations and ensure a flexible and energy-efficient network operation, novel optical switching nodes, known as Multi-Granular-Optical Nodes (MG-ONs), need to be developed [12]. These MG-ONs should encompass the following routing capabilities: 1) full-spectrum-fiber routing, 2) full-waveband routing, and 3) legacy wavelength routing. The MG-ONs should hierarchically integrate novel switching elements capable of operating at different levels: 1) full-fiber/spectrum level switching that supports more than 20 THz of bandwidth, including the S, C, and L bands, 2) flexible waveband switching, allowing the selection of specific bands (e.g., switching only the S, C, or L band) or any spectral segment, and 3) compatibility with legacy networks based on single-wavelength routing. To achieve this, innovative components need to be implemented, such as optical cross-connects with full-spectrum fiber switching capabilities and waveband-selective switches for flexible waveband switching, which would enhance current wavelength switching techniques based on conventional Wavelength Selective Switches (WSSs).

By deploying IP/optical MG-ONs with these capabilities, the envisioned IP/optical converged architecture can achieve high energy efficiency, allowing traffic to optimally bypass intermediate, power-hungry IP/packet routers. The optical links interconnecting MG-ONs would support capacities ranging from individual Tb/s single-wavelength channels to Pb/s aggregated spectral/spatial super-channels. Significant research efforts are currently underway to enhance the capacity and address the energy efficiency bottlenecks of current transponders/transceivers at switches, routers, and optical nodes.

Toward this objective, proposals have emerged advocating for the use of ultrahigh bandwidth optical modulators that rely on new materials and novel approaches aiming to extend the use of Analog Optical Signal Processing (AOSP) at the expense of more energy-inefficient digital DSP. In particular, the deployment of highly efficient optical Digital-to-Analog Converters (oDACs), which perform direct digital-to-optical conversion instead of power-hungry electronic DACs, is being explored. The use of such oDACs would improve the tradeoff between performance, energy efficiency, complexity, and cost in optical transmitters [13].

Additionally, significant efforts are being made to expand the capabilities of the fronthaul (FH). It has recently been proposed to replace passive splitters, currently used for distributing FH traffic in time-sensitive packet-switched networks, with subcarrier (de)multiplexers [14]. These novel modules would be more optical power-efficient and facilitate advanced multiplexing schemes in the FH, such as wavelength division multiplexing (WDM). This would allow for the flexible allocation of bandwidth, preventing the underutilization of available resources and thereby reducing the overall cost and power consumption. In the FH, the reliance on Time Division Multiplexing (TDM) Passive Optical Networks (PONs) poses serious latency constraints,

making it challenging to meet the stringent requirements of certain split options, like the 7.2 proposed by Open-RAN (O-RAN).

For this reason, discussions are ongoing about using WDM in Next-Generation PONs (NG-PONs) to establish virtual point-to-point links without relying on time-division multiple access. Furthermore, the use of subcarriers-based multiple access has been proposed as an alternative solution enabled by COH access systems. It is important to note that the requirements for transceivers used in FH applications differ from those of backhaul (BH) transceivers. In the FH segment, the power consumption and cost of each transponder are expected to have a more significant impact. This is one of the motivations behind the recent research focusing on reducing or eliminating the reliance on power-hungry digital signal processing for conventional transponders while enabling their capacity expansion.

The adoption of optical switches and COH transceivers in the FH is expected to become commonplace in the future, as it already is in BH. However, considering the differing requirements of FH versus midhaul (MH)—such as lower reach and data rates—it's important to consider that the accompanying transceivers and switching subsystems in FH will have relaxed specifications while still targeting improved cost and power efficiency [15].

Overall, all optical networking elements across the X-haul segments will be monitored and reconfigured by the intelligent control management and orchestration plane, to optimize the utilization of resources across the front-/mid-/back-haul continuum. This will minimize unnecessary optoelectronic transitions in the IP layer, thereby improving performance while minimizing operational costs and power consumption.

III. DIGITAL TWIN FEDERATION OF THE OWRAN WITH THE IP/OPTICAL X-HAUL

The proposed FDTN system for the IP-Optical X-haul will aggregate data from independent DTs, each collecting traffic-related information e.g., data from IoT sensors, and historical trends in delays and service times. These data can be shared between the DTs operating in different federated domains, or in order to maintain data privacy, they can be used to train ML models locally within each device, adopting, among others, Federated Learning (FL) approaches.

To achieve accurate estimations, the system can utilize Deep Learning (DL) methods, e.g. Deep Neural Networks (DNNs), including Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) and Recurrent Neural Networks (RNNs), along with Reinforcement Learning (RL) methods. Also, analytical and numerical methods, as well as traditional ML techniques, can assess the impact of traffic events, while shortest path algorithms, such as Dijkstra's algorithm, can be used to determine the optimal end-to-end routes. By integrating real-time and historical data with cutting-edge ML models that satisfy the reliability and latency requirements [6], the FDTN system will enhance overall network efficiency significantly. This gives rise to the term “*AI for Digital Twin*”.

There are two main options generally in the federation of FDTN training: (a) offline training and (b) online operation. In the offline training, DT models can be proactively trained prior to user requests, while the online operation involves instructing cars, sensors, and APs to serve end users.

The architecture of this concept consists of two primary layers: the DT layer and the infrastructure layer. The infrastructure layer includes all entities necessary for implementing the federation of the different DTs while the DT layer is implemented using edge/cloud computing machines/servers. Creating a real-time digital replica of the physical network infrastructure essentially means creating a sandbox in which it is possible to train models and test different scenarios before deploying them on physical network controllers.

In this context, more research activities need to be funded to examine methods and novel models based on dynamic and customizable traffic patterns to optimize AI-enabled failure localization, routing, resource allocation, and slicing. Also, there is a need to identify the quality of transmission depending on the changing conditions of the fixed infrastructure layer, taking into account the impact of Erbium Doped Fiber Amplifiers (EDFAs), optical nodes, and the 6G air interface, among others. The data-driven models to be developed for the implementation of the optical X-haul/OWC network DT need to prioritize minimal data collection without sacrificing the accuracy or reliability of desired DT tasks (e.g., virtual modelling, predictions). The DT network should be able to prioritize the communication services of certain traffic, enhancing the trend of “*Digital Twin for AI*”.

A twin object provides a virtual representation of the physical layer, enabling the modeling of various network functions and applications. These functions can be modeled using theoretical and experimental approaches [16]. Mathematical modeling often relies on assumptions and, therefore, cannot fully capture the network's dynamics with enough precision, while experimental modeling introduces significant errors during the experimentation process. The creation of a comprehensive control and orchestration system for future networks needs to cover a wide range of transmission technologies. This will be achieved by integrating existing solutions and developing new ones to facilitate end-to-end slicing, spanning from the access network to the X-haul and eventually to the core network. The proposed hierarchical system extends existing solutions to incorporate innovative optical technologies in the X-haul and integrates diverse access technologies, supporting both traditional radio and optical wireless connectivity. The ultimate goal of this system is to enable Flexible Fronthaul Solutions (FFS), dynamically coordinating RAN control based on X-haul capacity, and providing NaaS for operators

to request highly customized and orchestrated end-to-end network slices.

The orchestration platform will minimize energy consumption and enable full utilization of the frequency spectrum. It builds upon existing solutions standardized under ETSI, particularly focusing on leveraging advancements in optical technologies for high performance and energy efficiency. However, the seamless integration of these technologies into existing orchestration and network slicing stacks still remains a significant challenge. Emphasis is placed on enhancing software programmability across all network domains, especially in the end-to-end X-haul and the access domain orchestration, by employing widely established industry standards from various standards development organizations, such as TMF, IETF, ETSI.

While the orchestration platform facilitates the aforementioned end-to-end slicing in a seamless manner, it also promotes the highest level of granularity within each network domain by employing respective domain-specific orchestrators. A distinctive control system, known as the X-haul orchestrator, will govern the intelligent, programmable all-optical network fabric. This system operates across wavelength, band, and spatial dimensions, integrating Software-Defined Networking (SDN) orchestration across IP and optical network layers. It will enable end-to-end X-haul orchestration through the transport network and intra-data center networks, encompassing fronthaul, midhaul, and backhaul segments while significantly enhancing energy efficiency by minimizing opto-electronic conversions.

Furthermore, there is a strong need to extend the scope of the mainstream access segment by incorporating a discrete management and orchestration system for the OWRAN (Fig.3). The orchestrator functions as a central controller, seamlessly integrating advanced optical wireless technologies into the conventional radio access network. This integration not only significantly expands spectrum utilization but also enables dynamic resource allocation and elasticity, multi-user access, and interference management across the RF and optical domains, taking into account their heterogeneous nature.

IV. DISCUSSION

Optimal resource management in 6G networks can be achieved through AI-enabled end-to-end network planning, slicing, and orchestration enhanced by the FDTN operation. The end-to-end 6G infrastructure incorporates multiple

Fig. 3. The interconnection between different Federated Networks prioritizes the enhanced communication between various controllers and an overarching orchestration.

innovative technologies, ranging from efficient packet-based optical and wireless X-haul network coexistence and radio-optical wireless access network integration to advanced optical wireless and fixed transceivers, as well as novel switching technologies and future-proof transmission solutions for the X-haul segment, such as UWB. Orchestrating these building blocks effectively poses unprecedented algorithmic challenges, requiring solutions that ensure ultra-high energy efficiency.

New algorithms for end-to-end network operation and planning need to be developed to address these challenges, spanning integrated X-haul, wireless networks, and computing segments. In the realm of end-to-end network slicing and orchestration, a comprehensive control and orchestration system for future networks is envisioned, covering a broad range of transmission technologies. This can be accomplished by integrating existing solutions and developing new ones to facilitate E2E-NS, extending from the access network to the X-haul and the core network.

A. Flexible Functional Splitting

Next-generation access networks must offer not only increased capacity, improved manageability, lower costs, and power consumption but also enhanced flexibility to support societal progress in a sustainable way. The available networking resources are partitioned into dedicated “Network Slices (NS)” [17]. Each NS is customized to the application's needs in terms of bit-rate, latency, and reliability for various devices utilizing different network segments and corresponding resources. Proper orchestration ensures zero interference between different network slices. A distributed RAN can be supported by a slice if the Centralized Unit (CU)/Distributed Unit (DU) functions are virtualized on a general-purpose computing machine. The choice of FS drives the NS implementation, Quality of Service (QoS), and privacy issues, as different FSs have various mapping and continuity constraints [18]. Once novel approaches for Flexible Functional Split (FFS) allocation are released, each NS request will be supported even more efficiently, considering each's heterogeneous requirements while also optimizing the number of NFs installed throughout the X-haul.

B. End-to-End Network Slicing

Following the Anything-as-a-Service (XaaS) paradigm, strong interest has been focused on the NaaS model. End-to-End Network Slicing (E2E-NS) represents one way of offering the NaaS model, where cloudified network resources can be allocated to enterprises that operate their own virtual private networks [18]. Several challenges hinder the implementation of the long-debated E2E-NS. Although the Service Management and Orchestration (SMO) offers a generic framework to manage all the network segments, various data plane technologies (IP, Ethernet transport, optical transport) at the X-haul have custom SDN control systems that are hard to integrate to achieve E2E NS. Therefore, multi-layer transport connections and flows across these different technology layers are not yet appropriately coordinated by an overarching SDN orchestrator.

V. CONCLUSION

In this paper, we outlined the necessary innovations to support the 6G use case categories, focusing on the federation

of the different sub-segments/sub-domains. We presented a comprehensive vision, discussing the pivotal role of OFC and OWC technologies in transforming next-generation and future networks. The OWC can be a promising candidate for both space and underwater communications shaping a new frontier for 6G and beyond networks. The relentless demand for high-capacity to support 6G use case families, necessitates novel OFC technologies to provide ample spectral resources for accommodating the increasing traffic loads. This is the critical point or the “X-factor” of the 6G networks in order to optimally integrate the OFC and OWC technologies.

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